

USE OF SUPERCONDUCTORS IN INDUSTRY AND PRODUCTION AND ITS PROSPECTS

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Abstrakt: This article provides some important information about low temperature superconductors (LTS) and high temperature superconductors (HTS). At the same time, the application of superconducting materials in industry and production is explained with the help of some examples. The working principles of superconducting generators are studied. The use of BSCCO cuprate as a high-temperature superconductor and NbTi as a low-temperature superconductor has been studied.

Key words: Low-temperature superconductor (LTS), High-temperature superconductors (HTS), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Perfect zero resistance (perfect conductivity), perfect diamagnetism, flux quantization, and Josephson effect, high-field, high-current, wire-wound magnet, spinning at high speed.

Introduction

Superconductors conduct electricity with essentially zero resistance, avoiding many of the power losses in present electric power transmission, conversion, and use. Strong electromagnetic fields have so far been the principal application of superconductors, with widespread commercial superconductivity limited to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) electromagnets composed of the low-temperature superconductor (LTS) Nb₄₇Ti. Broader applications of LTSs have been hindered by the need to cool them with liquid helium (at or below 4.2 K). High-temperature superconductors (HTSs) that can operate at liquid nitrogen temperatures (between 65

and 80 K) promised ubiquitous applications that could escape the constraint of LTSs. Achieving the International Energy Agency roadmap to carbon-free economies by 2050 would be greatly facilitated by the use of nuclear fusion-generated electricity. HTSs have been used in prototype nuclear fusion reactors, thereby creating the opportunity to overcome the cost barriers that have so far prevented the commercial development of HTS technologies.

Applications of Superconductivity

From its inception until the coming of age of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in the mid-1980s, the U.S. superconducting wire industry was almost entirely dependent on wire procurements by Federal laboratories. This wire was primarily used in particle accelerator magnets for high-energy physics (HEP) .

Accelerators require huge amounts of superconducting wire. The Superconducting Super Collider will require an estimated 2,000 tons of NbTi wire, worth several hundred million dollars. Accelerators represent by far the largest market for superconducting wire, dwarfing commercial markets such as MRI.

The SSC is a racetrack-shaped collider that is expected to extend particle physics research to a higher level of energy-about 20 TeV-than has ever been achieved before. Sited in central Texas, the SSC is to be 54 miles in circumference-10 times the size of the Fermilab Tevatron-and may cost as much as \$7.2 billion. The superconducting magnets, which have experienced development problems, are expected to account for about one-third of the total SSC construction cost. In fiscal 1990, \$225 million was appropriated to continue development and begin construction of the SSC. The project is expected to be completed in 10 years.

Superconducting Generators

Superconducting generators enjoy three potential benefits over conventional generators. They offer better system stability against frequency changes due to transients on the grid. Because they can operate at higher magnetic fields (5 to 6 tesla), the size can be reduced up to 50 percent; this in turn could reduce capital costs

significantly. Finally, efficiency could be increased by 0.5 percent (a reduction in losses of around 50 percent). Even this small efficiency increase could result in fuel savings that would pay back the capital costs of the generator over its lifetime.

Although several prototype superconducting generators were designed and constructed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, General Electric Co., and Westinghouse Electric Corp. during the 1960s to the early 1980s, 15 these were never commercialized because there was no perceived demand for new generating capacity.¹⁶ Today, the United States has no significant ongoing commercial LTS generator program, although programs are continuing in West Germany, Japan, and the Soviet Union. Siemens in West Germany is proceeding with plans for an 850 megawatt (MW) commercial system, and tests of prototype components are expected to begin in 1990.¹⁷ A consortium of Japanese companies is developing a 200 MW generator for the late 1990s (the “Super-GM” project, see ch. 5).

Most studies indicate that LTS generators are only competitive with conventional generators at very high power ratings (500 to 1,000 MW). But with low load growth in the 1980s and continuing uncertainties about demand in the 1990s, there appears to be little enthusiasm among U.S. firms to put up their own cash for R&D on such large machines. In principle, use of HTS could make smaller machines more competitive, but estimates differ on how much. The refrigeration system would be much simpler, and this would lead to greater reliability and maintainability. But the application involves a high-field, high-current, wire-wound magnet, spinning at high speed, under large centrifugal stresses. HTS wires would have to carry current densities on the order of 100,000 Amps/cm² in a 5 tesla magnetic field to realize the large decrease in size possible. These requirements make the generator one of the most difficult applications for HTS. Beyond the turn of the century, there will be a market for new generators, both to replace older equipment and to accommodate growth in demand. The share of superconducting generators in this market is uncertain. But one thing is clear. Because it is likely to take at least 15 years to demonstrate a commercial system, the United

States is effectively conceding this market to its competitors unless it restarts its LTS generator programs immediately.

Features and applications of superconductor

There are four basic features of superconductivity: (1) Perfect zero resistance (perfect conductivity), (2) perfect diamagnetism, (3) flux quantization, and (4) Josephson effect. The examples of possible applications of superconductivity are shown in Fig. 1.

From the view point of application to electric power transmission/distribution, zero resistance and high current density are the two important characteristics. Because the resistance is zero, compact conductors that feature low transmission loss and high current density can be achieved. The zero resistance characteristic also allows the realization of compact high-field magnets that provide low heat generation and high current density. The applications shown in Fig. 1 (other than electronic-related applications) are the uses of conductors or high-field magnets. The applications of the Josephson effect include devices such as voltage standards, high-speed switching elements and superconducting quantum interference devices (SQUIDs) used for micro-magnetic field sensors, but this paper only discusses the applications of conductors and magnetic fields.

Fig. 1. Superconductor Applications

Application of superconducting magnetic field

Application of superconducting magnetic field The most basic application of superconductivity is superconducting magnets that can generate a high magnetic field at a compact size. Other than superconducting magnets, superconducting magnetic field is used by transformers, motors and linear motors. High-field superconducting magnet Superconducting magnets are used for the generation of high magnetic field which requires very large electrical power when using non-superconducting magnet. One example of commercial application of superconducting magnet is medical magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) that usually uses NbTi, a low-temperature alloy superconductor. The maximum magnetic field obtained using NbTi is around 8 T. To generate a magnetic field over 8 T, an intermetallic superconductor Nb₃Sn has been used. For nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), whose principle is the same as MRI but is used mainly for material analysis, higher field is required to have high resolution. When performing NMR at over 1GHz, a very high field of more than 23T is needed, but it is difficult to generate such high field with Nb₃Sn. Therefore, superconducting magnet using BSCCO wire is under development.

Conclusions

We have come to the following conclusion by analyzing the extent to which their use has developed from the creation of superconducting materials to the present. Superconductors are widely used in all important industries, including medicine, modern technology, industry, aerospace, nanotechnology, road transport system, aircraft and many other devices and fields. This is because the research results show that the use of superconductors in these areas provides the opportunity to save a large amount of energy. Humanity's need for energy is increasing year by year, if we do not step by step to use energy-saving technologies, energy problems will increase in the near future. To do this, we need to work on creating technologies that make superconducting materials more compact and superconductive at high temperatures.

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